

ROLE OF AYURVEDA IN RESTORING ARTAVA PRAVATTI IN A CASE OF PCOD- INDUCED OLIGOMENORRHOEA

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Article Received on 03 Nov. 2025,

Article Revised on 24 Nov. 2025,

Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17799218>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. Diksha Udaipure^{1*}, Dr. Priyanka Hajare², Dr. Varsha Jadhao³ (2025) Role Of Ayurveda In Restoring Artava Pravatti In A Case Of Pcod- Induced Oligomenorrhoea. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(23), 1514-1520. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Oligomenorrhea refers to irregular, inconsistent, or infrequent menstrual bleeding in women. It is characterized by menstrual cycles lasting more than 35 days or the presence of only four to nine cycles in a year. The menstrual pattern is generally normal before the onset of oligomenorrhea. As described by Acharya Sushruta, *Artava Kshaya* is a common menstrual disorder that arises due to sedentary habits, improper dietary patterns, and alterations in physical and mental health. PCOD is an ovulatory disorder in which a woman's ovaries fail to release eggs regularly as it develops multiple follicles, which develop into cysts in the ovaries over time. In contemporary science Oligohypomenorrhoea shows similar clinical presentation and its incidence rate is 22.5%, which has multiple causative factors of nutritional deficiency, hormonal factors, emotional and stress factors and psycho-sexual factors. Here is an attempt to study the case of Artavakshaya with Ayurveda treatment.

KEYWORDS: Oligomenorrhoea, *Artavajanana*, *Nidana*, *Tridosha*.

INTRODUCTION

Artava Kshaya is one of the common menstrual disorders which is caused due to sedentary lifestyle, faulty food habits and changes in physical and mental state. According to *Acarya Sushrutha*, menstruation that does not appear in appropriate time or delayed menses

associated with pain in yoni due to involvement of *Vata* and *Pitta* Dosha. Here, delayed means a duration of more than one month and scanty bleeding indicates bleeding lasts for less than 3 days. *Acharya Vagbhata I, Vagbhata II* and *Sharangdhar* also opine same characteristics for *Artava kshaya*. It can be correlated with oligomenorrhoea, by its sign and symptoms.

PCOD (Polycystic ovarian disease) is an ovulatory disorder in which a woman's ovaries fail to release eggs regularly as it develops multiple follicles, which develop into cysts in the ovaries over time. Women with PCOD and PCOS may emit more male hormones (androgens), resulting in infertility, irregular menstruation, hair loss, hirsutism, abnormal weight gain. *Artava kshaya* has also been mentioned in *Asta artava dushti* as *ksheena Artava*. Oligomenorrhoea is primary symptoms of PCOD. *Artava kshaya* can be seen in conditions like hypothyroidism.^[1]

In contemporary science Oligohypomenorrhoea shows similar clinical presentation and its incidence rate is 22.5%, which has multiple causative factors of nutritional deficiency, hormonal factors, emotional and stress factors and psycho-sexual factors. Here is an attempt to study the case of *Artavakshaya* with Ayurveda treatment.^[2]

CASE REPORT

Patient Information- The patient is a 23- year-old Unmarried Female, student, OPD No. 2531441 came to with a complaint of irregular menses for 2 years, associated with lower abdominal pain on and off and weakness for 6 months. She complains of feeling of heaviness and Swelling in her body. Patient had taken oral medicine for the same but was not relieved hence came to the PTSR Department of Mansarovar Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital and Research centre, Bhopal.

PAST HISTORY

Medical History- Taken Syrup Evicare (Himalya) for 1 year (on/off).

Surgical History- Not significant

MENSTRUAL HISTORY

Patient had attained her menarche at 13 years of age. Irregular menses after 6 months of menarche on/off.

Duration- 5-6 days.

Interval-50-60 days

LMP- 5/5/25

Number of pads used D1- 1 pad, D2-D3- 2pad, D4-D5- 1 pad

Pain-+ Clots- Absent, Foul smell- Absent, White discharge –Absent

Obstetric History- Nulliparous

Family History- Mother- Irregular menses before marriage.

Allergic History: No history of any allergy was found in this patient.

Clinical Findings

General examination - The patient was moderately built, with a height of 165 cm, weight 54 kg, and a BMI of 19.8 kg/m². Vital signs were within normal limits: blood pressure – 110/70 mmHg; pulse rate – 78/minutes, she was afebrile on touch, with face and eyes were pallor. Bowel and bladder habits were normal. Appetite was normal; however, her sleep was disturbed.

Systemic examination

RS- Bilateral Chest Clear

CVS- S1S2 heard, no murmur

CNS- conscious well oriented

P/A: Soft, Non-tender, No organomegaly.

Investigations

USG Abdomen on (17/06/25) - Uterus is Normal in size (6.9x3.2x3cm). Endometrial Lining is central and normal in thickness-5mm. Cervix is normal. Both ovaries are bulky in size and shows Polycystic ovarian morphology. Right ovary-10cc, Left ovary-10cc. Bilateral PCOD changes.

Hb%- 9.7 gm/dl,

T3-90ng|dl, T4-6.0ug|dl, TSH-2.0 mIU/L

Therapeutic Interventions

The patient was given *Shamana chikitsa*.

Follow Up

Date	Complain	Treatment
15/6/25	Irregular menses for 2 years, Pain during menses, Weakness, Fatigue	<i>Agnideepana</i> and <i>Aana pachan -Chitrakadi Vati</i> 1 BD (before food) <i>Vata-Kapha Shamana</i> and <i>aartava janana –</i> <i>Kumariasava</i> 10ml BD with Luke warm water after 30 minutes of food.
3/7/25	LMP-2/7/25, fatigue, mild relief pain during menses	<i>Chandraprabha vati</i> 1 BD (before food) <i>Punarnava mandura</i> 2 BD with Luke warm water after food <i>Tila kwatha granules</i> 3gm OD, (empty stomach at Morning)
05/08/25	LMP-2/8/25 weakness and fatigue on/off	<i>Punarnava mandura</i> 2 BD with Luke warm water after food <i>Tila kwatha granules</i> 3gm OD, (empty stomach at Morning)
04/09/25	LMP-1/9/25 relief in all previous complaints	<i>Kumariasava</i> 10ml BD with Luke warm water after 30 minutes of food. <i>Punarnava mandura</i> 2 BD with Luke warm water after food
07/10/25	LMP-3/10/25	<i>Medication Stopped</i>
04/11/25	LMP-1/11/25	<i>Medication Stopped</i>

Patient was on follow-up, next menses on 2/8/25, 1/9/25, 3/10/25, 1/11/25 she was observed for total 6 consecutive menstrual cycle.

Pathya Apathya Advised

She was advised not to take spicy, salty, oily, fast food, packed food etc. She was advised to add *kulatha*, *ghee*, *milk*, *lehsun* diet. She was asked to do *Pranayama* and *Yoga*, *Surya Namaskar*, aerobic exercise, brisk walk according to her body's ability daily.

Follow-up and Outcomes

Follow-up	Outcomes
After 1 st visit on 03/07/25	Interval between menstrual cycle of the patient reduced from 50-60 days to 30-35 days, and also, reduction in complaints like painful menstruation.
2 nd visit on 05/08/25	Interval between menstrual cycle was 30 days. And relief in weakness and fatigue.
3 rd visit on 04/09/25	Interval between menstrual cycle was 28 days there was complete relief in sign and symptoms. Polycystic ovarian morphology was absent in USG and no significant adnexal pathology were seen on last scan. And also, reduction in complaints like painful menstruation were also noticed. And CBC report was found to be within

	normal range.
4 th visit on 07/10/25	Interval between menstrual cycle was 30 days
5 th visit on 04/11/25	Interval between menstrual cycle was 28 days. and also, completely relief in pain during menses and weakness.

DISCUSSION

Artavakshaya is a *vata pitta* dominant *artava vikara*. Manitanance of *agnideepana*, *Amapachana*, and *Vatanulomana* along with nutritional supplementation through oral medications like *Chitrakadi vati*, *Kumaryasav*, *Chandraprabha Vati* and *Punarnava Mandura* showed encouraging results in the *artavakshaya*, with improvement in the symptoms of *Pandu*. Thus, the results suggest that These Medication can be established as an effective treatment for most of the complaints related to *artavakshaya*.

Chitrakadi Vati^[3] *Chitrakadi Vati* works mainly on *Agni*, *Ama*, and *Vata–Kapha* by virtue of *Katu Rasa*, *Ushna Virya*, *Tikshna–Laghu Guna*. *Chitrakadi Vati*, due to its *Ushna*, *Tikshna*, and *Deepana-Pachana Srotoshodhana*, *Vata–Kapha Shamana*, *Vatanulomana*, Improves Digestion properties, enhances *Agni* and removes *Ama* that obstructs *Artavavaha srotas*. Its *Ushna virya* stimulates *Apana Vayu* and improves pelvic circulation, promoting proper formation and timely expulsion of *Artava*. By reducing *Kapha-avarana* over *Vata*, it restores normal *Vata gati*, thereby helping regulate delayed or scanty menstruation.

Kumaryasava^[4]- *Kumaryasava* being *ushna veerya* and having *Agni pravarthaka gunas*. It is indicated in *shukra* and *arthava dusti*. *Agni vardhana guna* helps to induce menstruation and supporting *Rasa* and *Rakta dhatu* nourishment thus helps in maintaining menstrual cycles regular.

It is mainly indicated for *Agni Mandya* (low digestive fire), *Aamapachana* (digestive toxins), hormonal imbalance, and gynecological disorders like *Artava-kṣaya* (Oligomenorrhoea). Its *Srotoshodhana* Clears *Artavavaha srotas*, ensuring proper formation and flow of menstrual blood and *Rasayana*, *Dhatu Poshana* Nourishes *Rasa–Rakta dhatu*, improving tissue quality and supporting normal reproductive function.

Chandraprabha Vati^[5]- It is a classical *Ayurvedic* polyherbal–herbo-mineral formulation widely used in Urogenital, urinary, and gynecological disorders, as well as for *Vata–Kapha* imbalance, metabolic disturbances, and chronic debility. It contains ingredients like *Shilajit*,

Guggulu, Haritaki, Amalaki, Vidanga, Musta, Daruharidra, and other deepana–pachana herbs, formulated as a *Vati*.

It is indicated in *Prameha, Mutrakriccha* (dysuria), *Artava-kshaya, Arsha, Grahani, Gulma,* and *Apatarpana* conditions.

Chandraprabha Vati acts on *Artavavaha srotas* through its *Katu–Tikta rasa, Laghu–Ruksha guna* and *Ushna–Snigdha dravya* that correct metabolic blockages and digest *Aama*. Its *Tridosha-shamana* effect, especially *Vata–Kapha* balancing, restores the normal functioning of *Apana Vayu*, essential for timely menstruation. By improving *Agni*, enhancing *Rasa–Rakta dhatu poshana*, and providing *Srotoshodhana*, it increases pelvic circulation and supports healthy *Artava utpatti*. The formulation's *Yogavahi* and *Rasayana* nature strengthens reproductive tissues, helping correct delayed or scanty menstruation seen in *Artava-kṣaya*.

Tila kwatha granules^[6]- *Tila Ushna Veerya* increases the heat required for proper functioning of *Artavavaha Srotas*. Helps in normalizing delayed, scanty, or irregular menstruation. *Tila* has specific action in *artavavaha srotas* and *garbhasaya*. It is *snigdha-ushna, artava janaka, rasayana* and *dantya*. It helps in *artava* formation by *Rasa poshana*. Conversion of *rasa* to *rakta* helps in *artava* formation. *Tila* has *sookshma guna* which helps in reaching deeper *dhatu*s up to *sukra* level. *Agnimandya* can be corrected by ingredients like *vyosha* and *bhargi*. *Vyosha* improves the bioavailability of *Tila* in the *srotas* It is Rich in calcium, iron, zinc, vitamin E, which support healthy endometrium. Enhances *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu*, leading to better formation of *Artava*.

Punarnava Mandura^[7]- *Punarnava Maṇḍura* is a classical Ayurvedic herbo-mineral formulation primarily used in *Paṇḍu* (anemia), *Sotha* (edema), *Yakrit-Pliha Vṛddhi* (liver–spleen enlargement), and urinary disorders. Its action is a combination of herbal drugs processed iron (*Maṇḍura Bhasma*. It has *Raktavardhaka & Panduhara, Amapacana & Agni Dipana, Mutrala & Sothahara, Yakrit-Uttejaka & Raktaprasadaka, Srotoshodhana, Properties*. Pharmacological Mechanism are *Hematinic action, Hepatoprotective effect, Diuretic (Anti-edema) effect, Hepatoprotective effect, Anti-inflammatory & Anti-oxidant, Anti-fibrotic*.

CONCLUSION

Artava Kshaya is one of the commonly observed menstrual disorders in gynecological OPDs today. Several factors such as improper lifestyle and dietary habits, stress, and hormonal

imbalances contribute to its occurrence. *Artava Kshaya* often acts as a precursor to several serious health conditions like infertility, obesity, and depression. Therefore, it is crucial to address it at an early stage to prevent its further progression.

This study concludes that *Ayurvedic* medicines are effective in improving various parameters of *Artava Kshaya*, including menstrual interval, duration, and flow, along with a reduction in ovarian volume. Hence, *Ayurvedic* treatment can serve as a promising approach for the management of *Artava Kshaya*.

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